

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF AN AGRICULTURAL ECONOMY

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Annotation

In the current period, which is developing rapidly, the demand for agriculture is sharply increasing. But annanawi agriculture is not able to meet this need. It is for this reason that we need intelligent agriculture, which is able to solve this problem on the basis of more income and savings.

Keywords: GPS, Intelligent Agriculture, Artificial Satellite, IT Technologies, "Precision Peasant", Intellectual Farm, International Accounting Standards.

The 21st century is a century of Information Technology and development. The increasing needs of humans and its growth have been directly affecting nature and causing a variety of problems. One of these is food shortages. By 2050, the population of Planet Earth is expected to reach 9.6 billion and the need for food is expected to increase by 70 percent. This in turn creates problems such as limited land resources, water shortages in front of Agriculture. The development of Agriculture on the basis of digital technologies can solve these problems. Today, special attention is paid by the president of the Republic to the digitalization of Agriculture, the introduction of market principles in the interaction between agricultural entities, the introduction of modern resource-saving and intensive agrotechnologies. With the fact that the benefits of modern technologies are huge, they are a little expensive, in this respect their prevalence becomes a little difficult. But according to analyzes, the digital revolution in agriculture is approaching, and one of the main Turks to this is the development of unmanned vehicles, and this also systematically solves the problem of labor in agriculture. On November 29, 2017, our Honorable President SH.M.Mirziyoyev had signed a decree "on the establishment of the Ministry of innovation development". According to the decree, the introduction of modern tested forms of agricultural production based on the concept of "smart agriculture", which allows the rational use of existing land, water and other natural resources in the field of introduction of innovations to agriculture, maximum automation of agricultural production in the agrarian sector, serious improvement of productivity and financial indicators, as well as innovative ideas that, tasks such as assisting in the implementation of developments and technologies were established as the main areas of activity of the ministry. The deterioration of the ecological situation is a serious obstacle to the production of demand-level food, due to the increased cost of energy vehicles and a decrease in land productivity. It is possible to solve these problems through the concept of "Internet of things" for management, as well as modern technologies and innovative solutions, in short, intelligent agriculture.

Today, it technologies are actively used in the cultivation of grain crops, and this is called "Clear farming". In developed countries, agricultural farms are actively using IT technologies in their fields. Various sensors, satellite data and mobile applications are part of these. With

them, it is possible to determine the most favorable time for sowing seeds, watering, chopping, harvesting in the field. Choosing a convenient and fast route of delivery, control of warehouses for high-quality storage of fruits without problems. Opportunities such as contacting haridors, entering new markets, obtaining pre-orders provide economic development. Through mobile applications and sensors, it is possible to know which product will be in demand next year and grow exactly this one. This in turn also ensures the balance of supply and demand in the market. In addition, it is also much more likely that he will find an investor to grow a demanding product. In addition, through ready-made sales markets and demand from specific buyers, the farmer will be able to sell his product to the haridor he wants at the price he wants. Dalats such as the United States, China, India, Canada, Israel are countries that are actively investing in agrostartaps. We must and must develop this area based on the capabilities of our republic in the agrarian sector. Many farms sell their products cheaply. This is due to the fact that farmers are not interested in logistics, the study of export-import contracts and the search for new markets. Modern agriculture helps a lot in solving these problems without excessive problems. Cutting costs, increasing efficiency is the main goal of the development of a modern agricultural enterprise of any level and direction. The spread of modern agricultural technologies is slow. And the reason for this is in their price and in the absence of large investments that satisfy them. Agricultural holdings are even implementing the introduction of innovation step by step, distributing financial burdens and avoiding taking loans. In intellectual farms, uncontrolled transportation is developing. Self-walking tisms mounted on tractors and trucks not only reduce the human factor, but also stop grain and fuel theft. In addition to the camera and unmanned aerial vehicles supplied with high-sensing sensors , they can conduct research in the farm for several hours , create an electronic map of areas in 3D format based on the data they collect , perform such important tasks as calculating the vegetation index , protecting the Earth. Sensors and sensors are important parts of the intellectual farm. They provide continuous information about the condition of the entire farm's weathering, soil moisture levels, temperature, plant, health levels, fuel reserves, and such important information. Sensors are specialized in providing information about vegetation and productivity, natural diversity, sensors about the main features of the soil system. These greatly contribute to the preservation and full cultivation of the crop. These techniques can also be used with high efficiency in livestock and fishing. It is possible to determine the condition of cattle, milking time, homogeneity, symptoms of the disease. According to data, 70 percent of the world's fresh water is sorted into agriculture. 60% of it is wasted. This problem can also be solved through an intellectual system. The system can tell the farmer about the remote control of water pumps, the shortage of which is in advance. In India, the Nano Ganesh mobile app works in this regard and they have managed to save water, funds and time through it. Chile also has high achievements in this regard. They are watering fruit plantations through sensors, and this has helped them reduce water consumption by 70 percent. From this, extraterrestrial NASA with the US Geological Survey received satellite data on soil moisture in the country. Our country is located in the cozy God of Central Asia. In the Republic, the annual effective temperature is 26-30°, and the sunny hour is more than 3600, which allows you to get a harvest about once a year. The total land area of Uzbekistan is 44.4 million. ha (2004.) of which 50.8 percent is used by various agricultural enterprises, organizations and peasant farms: the sum of

which is the country's agriculture. For the development of Agriculture in our country, there is all the shariah, but the main part of Agriculture is still using the traditional method. This cannot match the growing food demand. In mamlatimda, the peasant and most of the farm are unaware of intelligent agriculture. First of all, we should pay strong attention to their legal literacy in this regard. From this, farmers and farmers will increase the interests of intelligent agriculture and try to apply it on their own farms. But it's not easy. Therefore, the fact that the state allocates large subsidies to this sector and gives preferential loans on the basis of low interest rates contributes significantly to the development of this sector. In addition, the fact that farmers and farmers try to attract investors is also a serious incentive. In doing so, our country should provide investors with stronger conditions for Yana. The development of International Accounting Standards in our country is an example of this. Our country has an ancient huge history and the influx of tourists from all over the world interested in our country is growing. Clegan must show tourists the potential of our country in agriculture. This in turn has a positive effect on the increase in the size of investors.

The following priorities have become the main reformer of the strategy, which includes: the widespread introduction of market principles in the procurement and sale of agricultural products, the development of quality control infrastructure, the promotion of exports, the creation of a favorable agribusiness environment and a value-added chain, which implies the production of competitive, high-value-added agriculture and food; This includes improving the efficiency and gradual redistribution of government spending by developing network programs aimed at improving labor productivity on farms, improving the quality of products, creating high added value; developing a system of Science, Education, Information and consulting services that provides for the use of effective forms of integrated knowledge and data distribution with the production of R & D, educational, information and consulting services in agriculture. After the decision was made, as a result of the work carried out on the basis of the strategy established from the dependence on the onset of the pandemic before much has passed, growth in the production of agricultural products has been observed. The role of Agriculture in the world economy is increasing dramatically in the following years. Therefore, the study of land, water, labor resources and their peculiarities, which are the main factors in the production of agricultural products, is important in the M iqyos of developed and developing countries. Agriculture is one of the main and oldest sectors of material production, supplying the population with food products and the bulk of raw materials for industry. Agriculture consists mainly of farming and animal husbandry, the two major sectors. These two sectors provide farming and livestock products for the population. Agricultural farming and animal husbandry also include a number of branches in which my products were originally processed. Approximately half of the economically active population, and in less progressive countries, more than 80-90 percent are often employed in agriculture. In developing countries, the rate is 10 percent. Social problems of the rural population, location are closely related to agriculture. Forestry is also part of Agriculture in several countries. The results in agricultural production made it possible to place our Republic among the countries where agricultural production is growing at a high level within the CIS. The main task of Agriculture is to meet the needs of the population of the country for food, and of the industry for raw materials, based on ensuring the

stable functioning of production and increasing its economic efficiency. Today, the annual consumption of per capita food is 55-70 percent. Retail imports of food are more than 40 percent. The need to establish various forms of ownership and forms of entrepreneurship in agriculture for the sustainable development of Agriculture at the level of demand of the laws of the free market economy, the effective use of land-water resources, the area of irrigated land, quality, material and technical resources, science and technology development, advanced technologies and their effective use, the main and working, it is advisable to justify ways to develop service in the village, save costs, set prices for its products and service, and increase the income of agricultural enterprises. As a result of agrarian reforms, agriculture switched to market forms of economic activity, and the balance of independent commodity producers increased.

Financial recovery of agricultural enterprises, the use of the credit system through state budget subsidies, crop insurance and a number of other works are carried out. However, the stable and rapid development of Agriculture has not yet been ensured. This problem can be solved by using innovation, modern techniques and technologies in agricultural production and new forms of economic development. Alternatively, sharp demands are made on the level of economic training of specialists of rural and other ASM enterprises. In order to meet these requirements, it is important to have an in-depth knowledge of the science of "agricultural economics". In agriculture, the land is publicly owned. It was embodied in the Chief figure of our state. Accordingly, as a result of the development of the relationship of its ownership, various forms of economic activity have emerged in agriculture to this day. Due to the variety of economic entities, depending on the economic interests, the specific goals of Ulama are also different. But at the same time, common aspects are also characteristic of them, such as the rational use of property objects, promising development of ulami, the rapid introduction of scientific and technical achievements into production. The objective necessity of the existence of state property is also explained by market imperfections. Among the "kemics" of such a market, the following stand out: external effect, the existence of natural monopolies, asymmetry of information, etc. Thus, changing the level of state intervention in the economy and the dimensions of state property reflects the internal aspirations of the economic system in terms of ensuring for each period and each country a certain acceptable ratio between economic freedom and economic intervention, micro and macroeconomic interests of the entire social farm, private and public entrepreneurship [3].

The following factors of practical importance determine the availability of public property in agriculture as a necessity: - the creation of macroeconomic conditions necessary for the functioning of the private sector, that is, the support of a network that is not of interest to private capital in the traditional way, which is commercially unprofitable, but determines the general conditions of reproduction for national; - implementation of a project that determines the acceleration of the processes of development of Science and technology and, on this basis, ensures the strengthening of the country's competitiveness in the world economy, with a high cost of Science and capital capacity and a high risk level; - creation of workplaces to develop a backward region in order to preserve hire, set low prices for products, eliminate socio-economic imbalances;

Ensure national and environmental security;-create conditions for the implementation of the contract and agreement and issue state bail. State ownership in agriculture of our republic is somewhat more effective in relation to exactly this form of economic activity in Western countries, a situation that cannot be explained only by the fact that a sharp reduction in state ownership, an increase in spending and a social conflict can cause. In our opinion, it is advisable to maintain the share of state property in the national economy in certain proportions in order to eliminate the discrepancy between the regions, create a single economic space. In countries moving to a market economy, the task of liberalizing the economy assumes a reduction in the monopoly of state ownership. Because a healthy market economy does not come out with a state monopoly, monopoly prevents competition. As a result of the nationalization of property, the contribution of public property in the economy decreases, it becomes mainly collective property, in some cases, civil property and private property. Therefore, "the most important task of the first stage of economic reform was to end the monopoly of state property and realistically form a multi-axis economy due to the privatization of this property," emphasizes President I.A. Karimov. As a result of the economic reforms carried out in agriculture on the nationalization and privatization of property in our republic, the contribution of state property in the network is sharply decreasing [4].

According to the data, a sharp decrease in the contribution of state property in agriculture coincides with the first period of nationalization and privatization of property (1990-1994). During this period, all state farms in agriculture began to be transformed into collective and company farms. As a result, it can be observed that the contribution of state households in gross agricultural product fell from 34.0% in 1991 to 2.2% by 1996. Public property contributions also tend to decline in later periods of economic reform. This is reflected in a sharp decrease in the number of state enterprises in agriculture. In conclusion, it should be noted that the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan has taken on the solution of several problems today, taking into account the important task that is in line in the development of Agriculture. This proves that the state is the chief reformer. Currently, the main focus of the Republican government is to ensure the development of all areas of agriculture, based on a unified science and Technology Policy. This is an extremely important issue. Because Science, new, efficient technology and advanced technology are the main bets on all your achievements.

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